

Relay Optics Aberrations and IFOV Depointing

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Table 1 below summarizes the results of 18 simulation runs with the CIP software at Lund Observatory. A-H are the runs reported in Lindegren (80-09-01), and 1-10 are the runs performed according to MATRA specifications and reported in three notes dated 82-05-25, 82-07-21, and 83-04-26.

Notations:

- IFOV ϕ : (geometrical) diameter of IFOV in as (30 as or 17 as)
- Tel.def. : telescope defocus (Δx) at grid in μm
- R.O.def. : relay optics defocus at photocathode in μm
- R.O.coma : max WFE of the form $W(y,z) = c.(y^2 + z^2)y$ ($y =$ along scan)
- G_{90} : geometrical blur circle on photocathode containing 90% of the energy, in as
- $\phi_{98\%}$: diameter of depointing region with normalized DC-component $\geq 98\%$, in as
- $\phi_{3\text{mas}}$: diameter of depointing region with phase error $|\Delta_1| \leq 3$ mas, in as

Table 1

Runs	IFOV ϕ	Tel.def.	R.O.def.	R.O.coma	G_{90}	$\phi_{98\%}$	$\phi_{3\text{mas}}$
A, 1	30"	0	0	0	0	15"	27"
3	30	0	0	$\lambda/2$	1"	15	27
4	30	0	0	2λ	3	15	27
5	30	0	50 μm	λ	9	14	27
B, D, 2	30	0	100	0	15	11	27
C	30	0	100	λ	17	9	27
6	30	0	50	10λ	19	10	27

E, F	30"	4 μm	100 μm	0	15"	10"	20"

7	30"	15 μm	100 μm	0	15"	13"	15"
9	30	15	200	0	30	4	4

8	17"	15 μm	100 μm	0	15"	3"	2"
10	17	15	200	0	30	3	1

Fig. 1. $\phi_{98\%}$ versus G_{90} for IFOV $\phi = 30''$.
(All Δx .)

Fig. 2. ϕ_{3mas} versus G_{90} for IFOV $\phi = 30''$ and different telescope defocus (Δx).